

Foaming of Phenolic Resin by Microwave Technology

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SUMMARY

This work consists of the development of a new process using a microwave oven to manufacture phenolic foam. The idea is to make in-situ foaming of a sandwich structure where an ecological intrinsic blowing agent is used. The goal is to obtain homogeneous foam with a density that is lower than 50kg/m^3 .

Keywords: Phenolic resin, Microwave curing, foam, sandwich materials, Aerospace

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich materials are well known for their high strength to weight ratio. In aerospace industry, these materials are often requested and different foams can be used in sandwich materials.

Phenolic foams are mainly used in the cabin sandwich materials. Their price is interesting, they are good insulators and they have good FST properties.

Currently, phenol foams are generally foamed in a thermal oven. However, processes in a thermal oven have several drawbacks, for example high thermal gradients. Thus, the developmental goals of microwave curing are to reduce the thermal gradient through volumetric heating, to decrease the process time through a higher heating ramp, and to save energy. Another advantage is to make in-situ foaming of the sandwich structure.

The goal of this research is to develop a new suitable process using microwave technology to manufacture homogeneous phenolic foams with a low density ($<50\text{kg/m}^3$) that could be typically used in airplane cabin sandwich structures.

Several nucleating agents were tested: fumed silica, layered silica and nanosoot. Several heating processes were studied as well.

The microstructure of the different foams was examined and their mechanical properties were determined via compression strength testing. Correlations between the heating process, the density of the foam, the nucleating agent and the mechanical properties were established.

RESULTS

A suitable microwave process was developed to manufacture homogeneous phenolic foams. The density of the foam could be varied. It has been proven that the intrinsic ecological blowing agent can be used successfully. The power of the microwave and the nucleating agent have a direct influence on the foam's microstructure and, thus, on the compression test results.

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